

varieties, we field-tested 12 resistant varieties and susceptible IR9752-71-3-2. We examined disease variation within year and interaction between year and variety during May-Oct 1987-89 in a randomized complete block design with two replications. Plants

were inoculated by stem-tape-inoculation method at maximum tillering and evaluated 2 wk later on 0-5 scale.

The results show differences among the tested varieties, although the differences varied from year to year. Tetep, Ta-poo-cho-z, and Guyanal

were best resistance donors in this test (see table).

Because the interaction between variety and year was highly significant, data for several years are essential in screening. ■

Pest resistance — insects

Resistance in rice to gall midge (GM) under natural conditions

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We evaluated 16 medium-tall rice varieties from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, during 1989 wet season to identify donors of resistance to rice GM and leafhopper (LF). Entries were planted in 13 rows at 10- × 15-cm spacing with three replications. Pest infestation was scored at 40 d after transplanting.

LF incidence was low during the season. GM infestation varied greatly among the entries (see table). Damage to the susceptible check exceeded the minimum threshold score of 3.

Resistance of rice cultivars to GM. Pattamhi, Kerala, India.

Designation	Cross	Mean score ^a	Average yield (t/ha)
RP2432-85-3-1	IR36/IET7916	0	2.3
R320-298	Samridhi/IR36	2	2.9
RP1579-1633-55-4-3	Phalguna/ARCC6650	2	1.5
UP2431-6-6-2	IR36/IET7918	3	2.2
RP2199-104-64-18-1	Phalguna/TKH6	3	0.85
RP1579-1633-55-43	6-17/ARC6650	4	1.4
RP2439-22-3-3	IR50/IET7918	4	2.2
RP1506-2709-688	TN1/ARC147668	5	2.6
RP2439-22-3-3	IR50/IET7918	5	1.7
HKR119	IR36/IET7916	5	2.3
Ratna		5	2.3
RP1990-979-1097-2	Sona/ARC14528	6	2.1
R296-471-2	CRI57-329/OR67-21	6	1.6
R321-43	Samridhi/IR36	6	2.8
R321-49	Samridhi/IR36	6	2.5
Sasyasree		6	1.1
LSD (P = 0.0.5)			0.5

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice scale

RP2432-85-3-1 exhibited a high degree of resistance in all three replications. Susceptible checks Ratna and Sadyasree scored 5 and 6, respectively. R320-298 had the highest yield. The average yield

of RP2432-85-3-1 was comparable. The two cultivars could be used as donors of GM resistance and for commercial cultivation in endemic areas. ■

Reactions of rice varieties to rice moth *Sitotroga cerealella*

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We studied eight rice varieties in the laboratory for resistance to Angoumois grain moth *S. cerealella* (Oliv.).

Adult moths from a laboratory culture reared at 29 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5% relative humidity were released in small glass jars for egg laying. Two hundred 24-h-old eggs were placed on 30 g of rice in glass jars, in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Hatched and unhatched eggs were counted 1 wk later.

Adults started emerging after 25 d. Loss in grain weight was considered an

index of susceptibility. Damaged grains were also determined.

Dry weight loss in all rices except KS282 and DR82 differed significantly, (see table). JP5 was most susceptible and DR82 least susceptible to *S. cerealella* attack. DR82, KS282, and Lateefy seem suitable for storage. A strong

positive correlation existed between number of adults that emerged and weight loss ($r = 0.93$), number of adults that emerged and grain damage ($r = 0.92$), and percent damaged grains and percent weight loss ($r = 0.98$).

These results conform with those from similar studies. ■

Dry weight loss, damaged grains, and number of *S. cerealella* adults that emerged in storage of rice varieties in Pakistan.^a

Variety	Dry wt lost (%)	Damaged grains (%)	Adults that emerged (no.)
DR82	6.1 a	14.1 b	21 bc
KS282	6.3 a	12.9 a	13 a
Lateefy	7.3 b	14.4 c	17 ab
DR83	13.3 c	14.5 c	24 cd
IR6	15.8 d	15.2 d	38 e
Bas 370	20.5 c	16.3 e	38 e
K. Bas	22.6 f	15.1 d	39 e
JP5	25.4 g	20.1 f	59 f

^a In a column, means with the same letter are not significantly different from each other at the 1% level by DMRT.